

Data Security and Privacy Using AES key Encryption and URL Encryption

Neha M

PG Scholar

Department of computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
neham2023b@mca.ajce.in

Meera Rose Mathew

Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
meerarosemathew@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Data are today an asset more critical than ever for all organizations we may think of. With the increasing use of digital technology in all aspects of life, the security of data has become a critical concern. The need for secure communication and storage of sensitive data has led to the development of encryption techniques that can ensure the confidentiality and integrity of data. One such technique is the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), a widely used symmetric-key encryption algorithm that provides strong security guarantees. In this paper, we present a study on data security and privacy using AES key encryption. We first introduce the basic concepts of encryption and the AES algorithm. We then discuss the different modes of operation of AES and their applications. We also examine the key management techniques that can be used to securely generate and exchange AES keys. In addition, we analyze the security strengths and weaknesses of AES and its potential vulnerabilities to attacks. Other challenges arise because the deployments of new data collection and processing devices, such as those used in IoT systems, increase the data attack surface. In this paper, we discuss relevant concepts and approaches for data security and privacy, and identify research challenges that must be addressed by comprehensive solutions to data security and privacy.

Keywords—data security, encryption, decryption,

AES Encryption , URL encryption

I. INTRODUCTION

Cryptography is a technique used to ensure the security of sensitive information by converting it into unreadable forms. However, symmetric key cryptography, which utilizes keys to encode and decode data, has been criticized for its vulnerability to unauthorized access by malicious individuals. This vulnerability stems from the fact that the cipher text generated by this technique can be visible to anyone. Symmetric key cryptography algorithms such as AES, DES, Triple DES, IDEA, and Blowfish have low tolerance for data encryption and provide low security. The main challenge with this technique is safely sharing the key with the intended recipient.

Public key cryptography, on the other hand, utilizes the RSA algorithm to provide high-level security, where public and individual keys are treated as valuable cryptographic assets. The existence of data is concealed within disguised text, making it invisible to anyone except the authorized recipient who possesses knowledge of its existence. Attempting to recover the original data without

authorization can take a considerable amount of time. Although public key cryptography provides enhanced security, it can be time-consuming to encode and decode data. The DES algorithm is commonly employed for document encryption and decryption.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There have been several studies on data security and privacy . Through literature review, we only found a few studies which were related to Data Security and Privacy. But all the contributions that are made in this field are getting more advanced day by day. Some of the information we obtained and discussed are given below:

Kumar Singh et.al [1] proposes the approach for securing data in cloud computing using AES encryption. The authors argue that cloud computing introduces new security risks and challenges, such as unauthorized access, data breaches, and insider attacks, which can compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive data. To address these challenges, the authors propose a three-layer security model that combines AES encryption, access control, and auditing mechanisms. They also conduct a comparative analysis of different encryption algorithms, including DES and AES, to evaluate their performance and security properties. The paper concludes that AES encryption provides a high level of security and performance for securing data in cloud computing environments.

Karnani et.al [2] proposes approach for securing data in cloud computing using hybrid cryptography algorithms. The authors argue that traditional encryption algorithms, such as AES and DES, may not provide sufficient security for cloud computing environments, which are vulnerable to various cyber attacks, including data breaches, man-in-the-middle attacks, and denial-of-service attacks.

To address these challenges, the authors propose a hybrid encryption algorithm that combines symmetric and asymmetric encryption techniques. They also propose a three-layer security model that includes data encryption, data fragmentation, and access control mechanisms. The paper concludes that the proposed approach provides a high level of security and performance for securing data in cloud computing environments. The research findings are based on experimental evaluations of the proposed approach using a cloud-based platform.

NIST [3] describes the Data Encryption Standard (DES), a symmetric-key encryption algorithm used for protecting electronic data. The document provides a detailed specification of the algorithm, including the key generation process, the encryption and decryption operations, and the key management procedures. It also includes guidance on the selection of appropriate key sizes and modes of operation for different applications. The publication was updated in 1999 to reflect changes in technology and to increase the key length from 56 bits to 64 bits. The document is intended for use by government agencies and contractors to protect sensitive information, but it is also used widely in commercial applications. The publication has been influential in the development of other encryption standards and has been the subject of numerous cryptanalytic studies.

Stallings et.al [4] The book provides a comprehensive introduction to the field of cryptography and its applications in network security. The book covers topics such as symmetric and asymmetric encryption algorithms, digital signatures, public key infrastructure, authentication protocols, and network security protocols such as SSL and TLS. It also covers important topics related to cryptographic attacks and their countermeasures, including brute-force attacks, cryptanalysis, and side-channel attacks.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The code implements a symmetric encryption and decryption algorithm using the AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) algorithm in CBC (Cipher Block Chaining) mode. The key and initialization vector (IV) used for encryption and decryption are hardcoded as byte strings in the code. The **encrypt** function takes a plaintext input and returns the encrypted ciphertext as a base64 encoded byte string. The **decrypt** function takes the ciphertext as input and returns the original plaintext as a byte string.

A. AES

The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is a widely used encryption algorithm that was introduced by the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in 2001 to replace the previously used data encryption standard (DES) from 1977. AES is a symmetric-key encryption method, meaning that the same key is used for both encrypting and decrypting data [1]. The algorithm is based on a cryptographic principle called a substitution-permutation network, which combines substitution and permutation operations and is efficiently implemented in both software and hardware systems. Unlike DES, AES uses Feistel networks and has a fixed block length of 128 bits, with key sizes of 128, 192, or 256 bits.

The implementation of AES involves the following steps:

1. Key expansion: The key provided by the user is expanded to generate a series of round keys, which are used in the encryption and decryption process.
2. Initial round: The plaintext is XORed with the first round key.
3. Main rounds: The algorithm repeats a set of operations (substitution, permutation, and mixing) for a specified number of rounds (10, 12, or 14 depending on the key length).
4. Final round: The algorithm performs a final round of operations that do not include mixing.

5. Output: The resulting ciphertext is produced.

B. DES

Data Encryption Standard (DES) is a powerful symmetrical-key block cipher that was developed in 1977 by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). The encryption technique used by DES is unique in that it takes a 64-bit plaintext input and generates 64 cipher texts as output. Although the key size for DES is 64 bits, only 56 bits are used for encryption and decryption, with the remaining 8 bits used for parity checking. The algorithm is based on the Feistel Cipher implementation and utilizes 16 rounds of Feistel structures to generate a 48-bit key for the cipher based on the predefined DES algorithm. Initially, the 64-bit input is divided into two 32-bit blocks referred to as L0 and R0, which undergo a series of Feistel rounds. This process is repeated for all 16 rounds of the encryption process, with the number of possible permutations increasing with each round, thus enhancing the security level. In the final round, the pre-output is created by exchanging L15 and R15, and the inverse function of the initial permutation is calculated by concatenating [R15, L15]. DES is commonly used for document encryption and decryption.

C. URL Encryption

URL encryption using an encryption key is a technique to secure sensitive information in the URL by encrypting it using a secret key. The URL is encrypted with an algorithm that transforms the data into an unreadable format that can only be decoded by using the same encryption key. This technique is used to protect data that is being transferred through the URL, such as login credentials or other sensitive information.

When using URL encryption, the data is encrypted before it is sent in the URL, and decrypted when it is received by the server. This ensures that the data is not visible to anyone who intercepts the URL in transit. The encryption key used to encrypt the data must be kept secret, as anyone with access to the key can decrypt the data.

The implementation of URL encryption key typically involves the following steps:

1. 1 Import the required modules The first step in the implementation process is to import the required modules. In this code, the following modules are imported:

- Fernet from the cryptography package: This module provides symmetric encryption and decryption algorithms.
 - Base64: This module provides functions to encode and decode data using base64 representation.
 - Logging: This module provides functions to log error messages and traceback information.
 - Settings from Django: This module provides access to the settings of a Django project.
- 2. Define the encryption and decryption functions The next step is to define two functions: `encrypt()` and `decrypt()`. These functions take a text string as input and return an encrypted or decrypted string.
- 3. Convert the input to a string Before encryption, the input text is converted to a string using the `str()`

function. This is done to ensure that the input is in a consistent format that can be encrypted.

4. Generate the encryption key An encryption key is generated using `Fernet.generate_key()` function. However, in this code, the key is retrieved from the `settings.py` file. The encryption key is a secret key that is used to encrypt and decrypt the text.
5. Encrypt the text The cipher suite is created using `Fernet`, where `ENCRYPT_KEY` is the encryption key retrieved from the `settings` file. The text is encrypted using cipher suite `encrypted(txt_encode('ascii'))` method. The encrypted text is then encoded using `base64.urlsafe_base64_encode()` function and returned.
6. Decrypt the text The encrypted text is decoded using `base64.urlsafe_b64decode()` method. The cipher suite is created using `Fernet`. The encrypted text is decrypted using `cipher_suite.decrypt(txt).decode("ascii")` method and returned

[1] IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATIONS

The implementation uses the Python programming language and the `PyCryptodome` library, which provides cryptographic functionality. The AES algorithm is used in CBC mode, which involves XORing the plaintext block with the previous ciphertext block before encryption to make the ciphertext more secure. The key and IV are hardcoded in the code, which is not recommended for real-world applications, as they should be generated and stored securely. Padding is used to ensure that the input data is a multiple of 16 bytes, as AES uses 16-byte blocks. [1] Base64 encoding is used to transport the ciphertext as it ensures that the ciphertext only contains printable ASCII characters, making it easy to transmit and store. Overall, the implementation provides a simple example of how to perform AES encryption and decryption in Python using CBC mode.

A. AES Encryption

1. Import the necessary modules

```
import base64
from Crypto.Cipher import AES
```

2. Define the encryption key and initialization vector (IV)

```
key = b'secretkey1234567'
iv = b'iv12345678901234'
```

3. Define the function to encrypt data using AES

```
def encrypt(data):
    # Create a new AES cipher object
```

```
    cipher = AES.new(key, AES.MODE_CBC,
iv)

    # Pad the data to a multiple of 16
bytes
    data = data + b"\0" * (AES.block_size
- len(data) % AES.block_size)

    # Encrypt the data using AES CBC mode
ciphertext = cipher.encrypt(data)
    # Encode the ciphertext using base64
for transport
    return base64.b64encode(ciphertext)
```

This function takes data as an input, creates an AES cipher object with the defined key and IV, pads the data to a multiple of 16 bytes, encrypts the data using AES CBC mode, and encodes the ciphertext using base64 for transport.

4. Define the function to decrypt data using AES

```
def decrypt(ciphertext):
    # Create a new AES cipher object
    cipher = AES.new(key, AES.MODE_CBC,
iv)

    # Decode the ciphertext from base64
    ciphertext =
base64.b64decode(ciphertext)

    # Decrypt the ciphertext using AES
CBC mode

    data = cipher.decrypt(ciphertext)

    # Remove the padding from the data
    return data.rstrip(b"\0")
```

This function takes ciphertext as an input, creates an AES cipher object with the defined key and IV, decodes the ciphertext from base64, decrypts the ciphertext using AES CBC mode, and removes the padding from the data.

B. URL Encryption

```
from cryptography.fernet import Fernet
import base64
import logging
import traceback
from django.conf import settings

#this is your "password/ENCRYPT_KEY".
keep it in settings.py file
#key = Fernet.generate_key()

def encrypt(txt):
    try:
```

```
# convert integer etc to string
first
txt = str(txt)
# get the key from settings
cipher_suite =
Fernet(settings.ENCRIPT_KEY) # key should
be byte
# #input should be byte, so
convert the text to byte
encrypted_text =
cipher_suite.encrypt(txt.encode('ascii'))
# encode to urlsafe base64 format
encrypted_text =
base64.urlsafe_b64encode(encrypted_text).
decode("ascii")
    return encrypted_text
except Exception as e:
    # log the error if any
    print(e)
    logging.getLogger("error_logger")
.error(traceback.format_exc())
    return None

def decrypt(txt):
    try:
        # base64 decode
        txt =
base64.urlsafe_b64decode(txt)
        cipher_suite =
Fernet(settings.ENCRIPT_KEY)
        decoded_text =
cipher_suite.decrypt(txt).decode("ascii")
        return decoded_text
    except Exception as e:
        # log the error
logging.getLogger("error_logger").error(t
raceback.format_exc())
        return None
```

1. Define the encryption key The first step in implementing URL encryption is to define the encryption key. This key is a secret key that is used to encrypt and decrypt the text. In this code, the key is retrieved from the settings.py file.

2. Convert the input to a string Before encryption, the input text is converted to a string using the str() function. This is done to ensure that the input is in a consistent format that can be encrypted.

3. Encrypt the text The text is encrypted using the Fernet encryption algorithm. The encryption process involves creating a cipher suite using the encryption key and encrypting the input text using the cipher suite. The encrypted text is then encoded using base64.urlsafe_b64encode() function to ensure that it can be safely transmitted as part of a URL.

4. Decrypt the text To decrypt the encrypted text, the process is reversed. The encrypted text is decoded using base64.urlsafe_b64decode() method. The cipher suite is created using Fernet. The encrypted text is decrypted using

5. Handle errors In case of any errors during the encryption or decryption process, the error message and traceback information is logged using the logging module. This is done to help diagnose and fix any issues that may arise during the encryption or decryption process.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper talks about the techniques AES encryption is a widely used symmetric-key encryption algorithm that provides a high level of security and privacy for data transmission and storage . It can be concluded that AES encryption is a highly effective and secure method for protecting data [5] .The implementation of AES encryption requires careful consideration of various factors such as key management, secure communication channels, and protection against side-channel attacks. AES encryption has been shown to be effective in protecting sensitive data from unauthorized access or use, and is widely used in various applications such as online banking, e-commerce, and mobile communication. However, it is essential to complement the use of AES encryption with other security measures such as firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and access controls to ensure comprehensive protection against data breaches. Future research should focus on developing new encryption algorithms that are resistant to quantum computing attacks and exploring new approaches for secure key exchange and management. Overall, the use of AES encryption is a critical component of any data security and privacy strategy, and should be carefully integrated into existing systems to ensure maximum effectiveness and protection.

VI. REFERENCES

- [2] Santosh Kumar Singh, Dr. P.K. Manjhi, Dr. R.K.Tiwari "An Approach towards Data Security in the Cloud Computing Using AES"
- [3] Sanjeev Kumar, Garima Karnani, Anju Mishra, Madhu Sharma Gaur "Cloud Security using Hybrid Cryptography Algorithms".
- [4] Data Encryption Standard (DES) by National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Published in: Federal Information Processing Standards Publication 46-3 (FIPS PUB 46-3), October 1999.
- [5] Cryptography and Network Security: Principles and Practice by William Stallings Published by: Pearson Education, Seventh Edition, 2017.
- [6] Swedha Shaji , Sr. Mercy Joseph "Cloud Security Using Hybrid Cryptography" ,2022.
- [7] Vinay Poduval, Ashish Koul, Daniel Rebello, Karunesh Bhat, Revati M. Wahul "Cloud based Secure Storage of Files using Hybrid Cryptography".
- [8] Punam V. Maitri "Secure File storage in Cloud Computing using Hybrid Cryptography Algorithm"
- [9] Shruti Kanatt "Review of Secure File Storage in contact Cloud utilizing Hybrid Cryptography".